

From Theory to Practice: A Hands-On Guide to the Deployment of Smart Classrooms

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Abstract. Smart classrooms are physical learning spaces equipped with ambient intelligence systems designed to collect data about the physical context, students, and teachers. They provide the latter with timely insights into the teaching and learning processes and help them make informed decisions. Key enablers for smart classrooms include sensors, ubiquitous computing systems, artificial intelligence, and computer vision techniques, among others. Despite numerous theoretical proposals in the literature aimed at various purposes, smart classrooms are not yet a plausible reality. This paper explores the challenges associated with designing and deploying smart classrooms and provides a comprehensive practical guide to help practitioners overcome these obstacles and advance the realisation of smart classrooms in real-world settings.

Keywords: Smart classrooms · Context-aware systems · Ubiquitous computing systems · Artificial intelligence · Learning technologies

1 Introduction

Smart classrooms are revolutionising education by leveraging digital, contextualised, and adaptive technological systems to enhance and accelerate both teaching and learning processes. These ambient intelligence environments rely on multiple interconnected ubiquitous computing systems consisting of sensors, Internet of Things (IoT) devices, and artificial intelligence (AI) techniques, able to collect and process data from students, teachers, and the environment [7], thereby supporting ambient-assisted learning. The knowledge provided by these systems assists teachers in making informed decisions [10]. Smart classrooms represent a significant evolution in educational environments, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of classroom dynamics.

Several systems have already been proposed to enable this smart *dimension* into classrooms (see Figure 1). For instance, optimal environmental conditions,

such as air quality, temperature, acoustics, and light, are well-known contextual factors that enhance students' concentration and motivation [2, 3]. Additionally, understanding students' emotions and moods can foster a positive emotional climate in the classroom, leading to enhanced academic performance [9]. Therefore, affective state monitoring systems, often deployed using smart wristbands, could also be integrated [5]. Similarly, video-based systems could be adopted to track students' movements or observe their behaviour. All these independent systems could coexist within the smart classroom environment and present the most relevant results to the teacher through the Teaching Assistant, a front-end that offers user-friendly visualisations and suggestions to the teachers. Unfortunately, most of the smart classroom solutions proposed in the literature remain theoretical, with truly functional smart classrooms yet to be implemented in real-life settings. This gap between theory and practice highlights the need for a practical view on the deployment of these settings. In this line, this article aims to provide a comprehensive discussion of the main challenges related to the deployment of smart classrooms, and suggest practical solutions to alleviate these obstacles. Specifically, we have addressed issues according to the following categories: data acquisition, data transmission, data security and privacy, and data and knowledge management.

2 Data Acquisition

Classrooms are dynamic, changing spaces that vary significantly in their physical characteristics, making each one unique in terms of dimensions, orientation, layout, architectural constraints, and design trends. For instance, classrooms in warmer climates might prioritise spaces with natural ventilation and cooling, while those in colder regions might focus on isolation and heating. Moreover, pedagogical approaches also influence classroom designs: primary schools might prefer open, flexible classrooms to enhance collaborative learning, while university classrooms might use more structured seating arrangements for traditional lecture-based instructions. Understanding these contextual factors is crucial for

Fig. 1. High-level diagram of a smart classroom ecosystem.

effectively deploying the proper sensing technologies. Below, the main challenges and potential corrective measures are discussed:

- *Greenfield vs brownfield projects*: Deploying a smart classroom over an existing classroom space (brownfield project) requires careful consideration of the existing physical infrastructure. Integrating new technologies into these established environments often involves technical, logistical, and installation burdens. To ensure compatibility with current systems and maintaining a seamless integration without compromising spaces, the components of smart classrooms should be designed as ubiquitous computing systems. On the contrary, designing a smart classroom from scratch (greenfield project) has less constraints but significantly increases the cost.
- *Trade-off between reliability and cost*: The use of low-cost sensors, while economically beneficial, often results in reliability and data accuracy issues. These sensors may not consistently provide precise measurements, negatively impacting the system’s effectiveness. This issue could be mitigated by duplicating sensors to ensure comprehensive coverage and redundancy (*e.g.*, cross-validating data by placing temperature sensors at various locations within the classroom).
- *Heating*: Densely packed electronic devices are prone to heating problems, leading to sensor performance degradation, drift, or even failures. Proper cooling solutions and regular calibration are necessary to maintain optimal sensor functionality.
- *Energy consumption*: Wired sensing devices are capable of providing consistent power without requiring frequent maintenance, but they involve high installation costs due to the complexity of integrating cables into existing classroom infrastructure, sometimes requiring significant alterations to the physical space. Conversely, battery-powered sensing devices offer greater flexibility and ease of installation, but regular maintenance is needed as batteries need to be periodically replaced.

3 Data Transmission

Smart classrooms require effective and reliable transmission and communication of data among the numerous devices and systems deployed in them. This data flow is pivotal to guarantee contextual monitoring and real-time interaction between people and their environment. However, communication networks and channels might present a number of challenges to be considered:

- *Network infrastructure*: The current network infrastructures in educational centres are often inadequately equipped to handle the number of devices and systems required for smart classrooms or struggle with bandwidth limitations and insufficient coverage. For this reason, smart classrooms should operate on a separate network enabled by latest networking solutions.
- *Wireless channel characterisation*: The coexistence of a wide variety of sensing devices and communication systems can lead to interference issues due to

the increased number of antennas. Therefore, the placement of these devices cannot be arbitrary, necessitating proper wireless channel characterisation analyses in each specific scenario, which is a laborious task [4].

- *Interoperability*: Interoperability is a critical challenge in intelligent environments, as it facilitates the seamless interaction of multiple, heterogeneous components [1]. Interoperability in smart classrooms could be implemented using a hierarchical multi-agent system [6], where each agent controls a specific element of the environment, and the cooperation of all these agents results in an emergent intelligent behaviour that adapts the environment to optimise the learning process. However, practical interoperability aspects must be addressed at multiple levels. For instance, the inclusion of closed, commercial systems (*e.g.*, wearable devices or video-camera providers) should be carefully studied, to ensure that real-time access to data is feasible. In this line, interoperability challenges can be more easily managed when dealing with open-source hardware and systems. Devices must transmit and exchange data through middleware platforms or APIs over standard communication protocols, such as TCP/IP, HTTPS, or MQTT. Moreover, the meaning of the exchanged data must be preserved across different systems, thus encouraging the use of ontologies and metadata annotations to properly interpret the data’s semantics.

4 Data Security and Privacy

The massive sensorisation of smart classrooms raises serious concerns regarding data security and privacy, especially in schools where the majority of their population is underage. The main challenges to consider are listed as follows:

- *Vulnerabilities in devices*: As with any context-aware environment, the infrastructure of smart classrooms is susceptible to cyberattacks that can compromise devices and systems. The heterogeneous nature of devices in smart classrooms complicates the implementation of standardised security measures as old and new technologies might co-live. Keeping devices updated is crucial to minimise the impact of vulnerabilities.
- *Secure data transmission*: Effective security management practices are needed to handle encryption protocols properly and ensure secure, authenticated data transmission. To that end, devices must be configured with public-key certificates managed by a trusted administrator so that the communication between devices guarantees confidentiality, integrity, and authentication properties. For instance, it is imperative to implement robust security protocols, such as securing the MQTT channel or the multi-agent system architecture with a TLS/SSL layer, along with strict access controls like MAC filtering and role-based access control. Note that deploying a specific network infrastructure in the smart classrooms facilitates security management.
- *Compliance with data protection regulations*: The collection and analysis of students’ physiological biosignals to detect emotional states, or the use of

microphones and cameras to assess expressions, body language, and postures, not only poses privacy risks but also raises ethical concerns regarding the responsible use of such data. These systems must incorporate privacy-preserving techniques common to ubiquitous computing systems, such as using pseudonyms or privacy-aware audio/video surveillance techniques to protect individuals' identities and applying statistical disclosure control techniques to protect individuals' data footprints [8].

5 Data and Knowledge Management

Efficient data management is crucial for collecting, storing, and analysing the information generated by the various sensing devices and systems within the smart classrooms. However, the heterogeneous nature of this data complicates these tasks, as discussed as follows:

- *Data management*: Smart classrooms include a number of devices that generate a very large amount of data (*e.g.*, video footage, sensor data...). To maintain operational efficiency, it is crucial that raw data remains within its originating system. Hence, only the knowledge and insights that are relevant and necessary for other systems should be transmitted. This minimises unnecessary data transfer, reduces the risk of data breaches, and ensures that each system operates independently while still contributing to the overall functionality of the smart classroom as a whole.
- *Knowledge management*: As AI is a key enabler of smart classrooms, such intelligence can emerge from simple rule-based systems that detect specific cases deterministically. For instance, a red indicator might be activated if there is excessive noise for more than five minutes, or a notice informing that half of the students are distracted might appear on the Teacher Assistant. However, the true potential of AI in this context lies in its ability to identify patterns or make predictions through machine learning models operating within various smart classroom components. These models need to detect particular situations and must be trained on specific datasets which, unfortunately, are scarce.

6 Conclusions

Smart classrooms are gaining the attention from the research community as an innovative and efficient paradigm for enhancing teaching and learning processes. Founded on ubiquitous computing principles, these environments leverage sensors and context-aware systems to capture vast amounts of data for further processing using artificial intelligence techniques. Notwithstanding, the practical deployment of smart classrooms is far from straightforward. In this article, we have discussed the main obstacles when deploying the underlying smart classroom technology in real-life settings. Specifically, we have detailed numerous challenges that must be addressed, including the implementation of brownfield

smart classrooms, the reliability and cost of the sensing layer, heating and energy consumption issues, network infrastructure and wireless channel characterisation, interoperability aspects, devices vulnerabilities, secure data transmission, compliance with data protection regulations, and data and knowledge management. Future research efforts should focus on integrating all components of a smart classroom into a real learning environment and evaluating its suitability on the teaching and learning processes.

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